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Abstract book

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MR guided brachytherapy for gynecological cancer

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Malignant tumors of gynecological localization still represent a major epidemiological problem in Serbia. According to the data from the Cancer Registry, by frequency, they account for more than 16.5%, and by cause of death more than 13% of all malignant diseases in the female population. A multidisciplinary approach is the basis of treatment, where surgery, radiotherapy, and chemotherapy are used in a different relation, according to the localization of the primary tumor and the stage of the disease.

Brachytherapy (BRT) due to the high contact doses that are achieved in tissues near the radioactive source in the applicator system, has an irreplaceable role in reaching the required radiotherapy dose in the tumor region, which is necessary to achieve local control of the disease. However, for the same reason, brachytherapy also poses a high risk for radiation damage to surrounding healthy organs and tissues – organs at risk (OAR).

The implementation of modern CT and MR imaging in brachytherapy created conditions for the development of 3D brachytherapy volume-based, "image-guided" planning. Superior imaging provides high precision in the visualization of soft tissue structures in the pelvis, both tumor tissue and organs at risk, which creates conditions for high precision in the delivery of the brachytherapy dose. The brachytherapy dose is prescribed and monitored in small volumes of tissue, and according to GEC-ESTRO recommendations, dose-volume parameters are defined for each of the target and organ risk volumes that need to be fulfilled during BRT planning.

The BRT dose is prescribed to three different target volumes: GTV, HR-CTV, and IR-CTV, while the tolerated doses for organs at risk are monitored in small volumes of their wall: 0.1 ccm, 1 ccm, and 2 ccm.

Such high control in the delivery of the brachytherapy dose, which is ensured by the high precision and image quality of MR imaging, en-

ables a highly personalized form of radiation therapy, adapted to the anatomical characteristics of each patient, and results in achieving better local control of the disease while at the same time reducing the frequency and grade of irradiation toxicity.

Keywords: 3D brachytherapy, gynecology, radiotherapy

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